

Floor plan extraction from digital building models

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Official geodata is increasingly published not only in the form of 2D maps but also in 3D, mainly as city models in CityGML. Usually, the outer shell of buildings is captured in such models, but they may also involve more intricate details. Even more detailed building models are generated during the planning process for new buildings and renovations. Nowadays, owners and operators produce these models in digital form during the design, planning and execution. Then, an as-built version is archived for the remaining lifetime of a building. In the future, digital building model submission may even be required to obtain a building permit. At the same time, public interest in detailed information about public and semi-public interior spaces is increasing, for example about their accessibility, the localization of barriers, destinations (e.g., contact persons in public administration), resources (e.g., defibrillators) or to get a first impression in advance (e.g., virtual open day).

Since the context of creating and capturing geodata and building data is fundamentally different, there is hardly any integration. Indoor data for maps and navigation models is manually captured or at best derived in undocumented semi-automatic workflows. The project LevelOut sets out to develop automated methods and services to make detailed indoor data from digital building models selectively available for the population of city models, map and navigation services (in the form of 2.5D floor plans). Towards this end, we develop a platform to check building models for the required information, extract selected and simplified indoor data and convert it into various formats (see Figure 1). As conversion targets, we consider two application schemes of the Geographic Markup Language (GML), CityGML LoD0 Indoor [1] and IndoorGML [2], as well as the indoor portion of OpenStreetMap (OSM Indoor). As input, we rely on data in the format IFC (Industry Foundation Classes), the most widespread standardised data exchange format for digital building models. With this research and development, we aim to provide a workflow and software for systematic access of floor plan data in IFC [3,4]. We start at both ends of integration by looking at the detailed structures of the source and target models in parallel.

OSM Indoor is but one of the various extraction targets. We focus on geometry with Simple Indoor Tagging and additionally consider Simple 3D Buildings (S3DB) for basic tagging of 3D properties of the building. The data created could be directly fed into OSM or

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may serve as a viable base for further mapping. There is only little work on IFC-to-OSM conversion. A recent attempt was made with the addition of IFC-functionality to the JOSM plugin 'Indoor Helper' [5]. The plugin is under active development, but it lacks a general approach on the IFC side as well as systematic coverage of the heterogeneous options to represent geometry in the IFC schema.

Figure 1. LevelOut Platform with input and output.

The second extraction target, CityGML, is a GML application schema for 3D city models and an exchange format issued as an international standard by the OGC. It provides a conceptual model for 3D city objects with their semantics, geometry, topology, appearance and other attributes. There are many different application scenarios for CityGML, including urban planning, simulations, real estate management, 3D cadastre, among others. There is a wide range of research on IFC-to-CityGML conversion. Konde et al. were first to put a focus on floor plans [6]. They demonstrate various options to model floor plans in CityGML based on inclusion of particular elements (walls, openings, rooms) and on choice of spatio-semantic representation (0-, 1-, 2-dimensional abstractions) resulting in different LoD. They also show two approaches to extract floor plans from IFC: either relying on the original IFC geometry or on preprocessed triangulated geometry.

IndoorGML is the third extraction target. The main purpose of this standard is to support navigation and location based services. It implements a cellular space model concept to represent geometry and topology. For the purpose of producing IndoorGML data from IFC, Diakite et al. recently published an open source solution [7]. Their tool carries out a conversion in three steps: parsing IFC data while organizing it as Linear Cell Complex (LCC) data structure, processing the data to generate IndoorGML cell boundaries, nodes, edges, and topological relationships and, finally, exporting the data as IndoorGML files.

In the current stage, we have already investigated and examined the OGC schemas (CityGML, IndoorGML) and analysed the OSM schema and tagging approaches. From the set of target models, we derive a common model that will have near-trivial mappings to OSM Indoor, CityGML and IndoorGML and serve as an intermediate model. In a subsequent step we are going to identify commonalities and shared characteristics across the three models in order to determine features to be included in the intermediate model. Preliminary considerations include geo-coordinates, rooms and space-defining surfaces and elements.

Next, we identify relevant information in the source model that can be used to establish the 2.5D geometry and topology of navigable spaces for the target models. IFC exposes a variety of geometry modelling constructions from CAD software, mainly following the modelling paradigm of constructive solid geometry (CSG). So far, we have identified the following principal representation options in IFC-conformant building models:

a) Direct floor plan representation in 2.5D: Here, we have 2D representations in 3D space, usually located at finished floor level for a particular storey. We distinguish two versions: space boundaries (floor and wall element footprints) versus abstract representations of space-defining elements (e.g. wall axis).

b) Extraction from CSG: Spaces and constructive elements are often represented as solids, which result from extrusion of a planar shape. If the solid has been extruded in the z-direction, its base shape and extrusion height can be used as a 2.5D representation.

c) Projection onto floor level: If the geometry is not in CSG form with extrusions, but in the form of BREP (boundary representation) or a mesh, then projection followed by a simplification of the projection result is a possible way to extract the 2.5D representation.

In contrast to OSM, where semantics are attached to geometry via tags, the IFC data model is founded on a reciprocal principle with geometry attached to a semantically typed object as an attribute. Associations between objects such as physical contact or spatial containment can possibly carry geometric attributes as well. Thus, while in OSM the geometric model elements are charged with meaning through tags, in IFC objects with meaning are equipped with geometric properties. We aim to transfer semantic meaning and attributes to the target models. Whether this is possible and how much effort it requires, will depend on the type of geometry and according extraction method mentioned above.

We have investigated the IFC standard for relevant entity types (classes) and give a brief overview in the following: For 2.5D floor plans, we need to process elements per building and storey and thus exploit the spatial hierarchy, an essential concept in IFC based on aggregation relationships as expressed with the class *IfcRelAggregates*. Considering the work's background in extracting floor plans for map services and navigation models, the geometry attributed to objects of the class *IfcSpace* represents the walkable space. For the geometric representation of *IfcSpace*, different concepts are provided in IFC corresponding to the representation principles above: 2D curves as footprints (a), swept - extruded and revolved - area solids (b), clipping with half space solids and boundary representation (c). Using extruded area solids as an example, the geometry is of class *IfcExtrudedAreaSolid*. An extrusion profile is then represented as an attribute of class *IfcArbitraryClosedProfileDef* or *IfcArbitraryProfileDefWithVoids* - if voids exist due to building elements in space such as columns. These profiles can be used as 2.5D floor plans. The geometry description is further placed in a local coordinate system with origin of class *IfcCartesianPoint* and axis directions represented with class *IfcDirection*. Besides *IfcSpace*, further classes are relevant for the work's purpose, e.g. elements for vertical navigation, i.a. *IfcStair*, *IfcDoor*, *IfcRamp* or *IfcTransportElement* as well as space-bounding elements, i.a. *IfcRelSpaceBoundary*.

At first, we check the given building models and extract the required entities and their attributes manually in order to derive automatic procedures later on. Furthermore, the relevant building elements of the demonstration object need to be exported losslessly from the authoring application into the IFC format.

After identification of the relevant entities, we are developing a three-stage process for the actual population of target models from IFC.

1. Building model enrichment: Information that can be represented in IFC will be reintegrated into the building model instead of being promoted to the intermediate model only.
2. Building to intermediate model: This is an essential step which will be covered with a flexible rule-based mapping.
3. Intermediate to target models: Following a careful design of the intermediate model, this step should be simple.

We will test the processes with data from public buildings, two sets of university campus buildings as well as one newly built municipal administration centre. From the assessment of the building data, we will also document modelling and export guidelines for BIM authoring software. As far as possible, the demo data will be made publicly available as open data. More importantly, the conversion procedures will be published as open source and a respective conversion service will be offered online.

In summary, our work provides practical benefit in terms of tools to support the mapping process as well as a scientific contribution in terms of spatial data integration and expert involvement via domain-specific languages. The practical benefit of the conversion is obvious: building owners can publish data of their publicly accessible spaces to aid volunteer mapping efforts. In the future, we also want to tackle updating, checking, and comparison with existing OSM indoor data. Scientific contributions are made in different ways: First, a generalised indoor model based on the OGC Indoor Feature Model is provided. The audience of this conference may find particularly interesting how OSM data fits with the generalised model. The generalised intermediate model will not only facilitate the integration of IFC with multiple targets besides OSM, but also the integration of OSM with multiple sources besides IFC. Further, we explore methods for flexible data integration with domain specialists and expert community involvement. To OSM this could be relevant in the light of the flexible and fluctuating tagging schemes requiring adjustments to conversion processes. Finally, but beyond the scope of this conference, we evaluate the applicability of bidirectional integration methods with multiple sources and targets via intermediary formats.

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